

A Pragmatic Analysis of Taboo Expressions in Idoma Language

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Abstract

Taboo expressions are words or phrases that are considered forbidden to be used in a particular culture or society. In Idoma language and culture, they are forbidden to be used except by certain people (old ones) in certain situations. This research carried out a pragmatic analysis of the taboo expressions in Idoma language, focusing on the politeness and euphemism of their usage. The study adopted qualitative, descriptive, and discursive research approaches which hinged on the proposition of Brown and Levinson's (1978) politeness theory principles. The analysis revealed that the Idoma taboo expressions are classified into various groups depending on the usage. They are social related, sex related, or cultural related. Taboo expressions are prevalent in the Idoma language with different functions, but people avoid using them because of their implications in the society, and opt for euphemisms. They are used by the elders, sometimes, to correct youngsters about their immoral acts which may bring psychological shame on them. To avoid the extinction of some vital expressions in the language, this study recommended that taboo expressions can be used in private discussions – among couples, friends, and relatives. Also, writers of Idoma texts should endeavour to document aspects of the Idoma taboo expressions. Having contributed to the extant literature on the Idoma language, the research called for further studies to be carried out on the cultural and ideological implications of taboo usage, and how taboo expressions should be taught to the young so as to know how to use or avoid them.

Keywords: Taboos and Taboo Expressions, Taboo Expressions and Euphemisms, Pragmatics, Idoma People, Idoma Language, Politeness Theory

Introduction

Communication skill is a crucial component of language use; in African societies, especially, this ability is becoming more and more important to the community. Humans use language as a vital tool for interpersonal communication. Language is a universal phenomenon. Every society uses language to meet a range of needs, some of which are positive and some of which are negative. According to Michael (2018), language is perceived as a two-edged sword which requires to be wielded carefully because it has the power to pacify, fix, control, or extinguish. Every society has linguistic norms that consciously and unconsciously direct people towards the words and expressions to be used at diverse instances and involving individuals of various sexual backgrounds, ages, social classes, etc. because of the negative effects of language use and those to be avoided in their daily interactions.

In the field of linguistics, pragmatics deals with study of how language is used in related to context, or how meanings beyond literal interpretations are influenced by context. It explores the systematic ways employed by speakers while using the language to accomplish their communication objectives and looks at the social, cultural, and contextual elements that influence language use (Levinson, 1983). The phenomena of pragmatics cover include implicature, deixis, speech acts, and politeness, all of which add to the complexity and richness of human communication.

Taboo words are generally referred to as linguistic taboos. They are words that, when uttered in public, are regarded as acts of immorality because they are seen as violations of certain moral codes. Such words or expressions often include words that relate to body parts, body secretions, etc Michael (2018). As a result of the shameful, immoral, and provocative nature of these words, when native speakers of the Idoma language come across them in their speech, they employ euphemisms rather than using such words directly.

It is of great importance to understand the intricacies between formal, neutral, and informal expressions. Hence, it is essential to address these differences while using the language. In order not to violate Idoma culture in language use, users of Idoma avoid using taboo words. Also, writers of Idoma language books do not use them in their texts. Hence, it has opened a breach in the learning and teaching processes of the language. In order words, Idoma is not being taught and learned in its complete forms; after all, taboo words are also parts of the Idoma language. This creates a constraint on the language used to a certain level.

Scholarly works exist on the Idoma language; however, few contributions exist on the aspects of taboo words or expressions in the language. Drawing from the above, this particular research seeks to investigate the use of taboo words or expressions in the Idoma language. This includes the identification of various forms of such words and expressions in the language and the context in which they are used.

Literature Review

Conceptualising Taboo and Taboo language

There have always been existence of taboos even though the phrase was originally coined by Captain Cook in the latter part of the nineteenth century, 1977 precisely), when he was dispatched to Tahiti. He reports the word taboo as signifying something forbidden (Allan and Burrige, 2006:23). Allan and Burrige (2006:2-3) define taboo, or 'tabu', as a Tongan phrase that implies a person, item, or conduct that is dangerous and must be avoided. It is actually considered to have a connection with somebody or a thing that is avoided or prohibited to speak about. To give a broader explanation of the above statement, Trudgill (2000:18) asserts that:

Taboo can be defined as activity that is considered to be supernaturally forbidden or viewed as immoral or improper; it deals with behaviour that is prohibited yet repressed in an apparently unreasonable manner. In language, taboo refers to things that are not expressed, specifically phrases and expressions that are not utilised.

Drawing from the statement above, a linkage exists between taboo behaviour and taboo language. They are regarded as immoral in some circumstances; hence, both are forbidden. Fairman (2009:27), in support of the idea that taboo acts behaviours and taboo expressions or words exist in every society. For instance, the act of incest is considered taboo since it involves sexual affair, that is strictly outlawed in society. Similarly, words referring to incest, like "motherfucker", are considered taboo as they imply the action.

Taboo language, or expressions, are words or phrases that are considered forbidden to be used in a society. Michael (2018) defines linguistic taboo being any word, phrase, or subject that, when publicly stated, generates discomfort and a feeling of shame and is insulting to the hearer's sensitivities or beliefs. Mercury (1995:30) further explains taboo language as "obscure language" or expression whose usage is restricted in the public be it overtly or covertly. Therefore, its usage is confined to the private communication. Explicit education is regulated by television network authorities, global course and book publishers, whilst implicit constraints are established, for instance, by parents by using euphemisms instead of taboo expressions.

Today's frequent use of taboo language reduces its impact. According to Michael (2018), despite being a forbidden term in Britain and the United States, attitudes towards it are more tolerant today than in the past. Although taboo words and expressions can be seen in newspapers, fiction works, magazines, movies, music, and television shows, their prevalence does not reduce their effectiveness. Taboo language can be heard in films, music, and popular literature, so second language speakers receive a mistaken sense about which terms are taboo and which are not (Mercury 1995:35).

Taboo Expressions and Euphemisms

According to the Encyclopaedia Britannica (2002), euphemisms is a substitution of taboo words or expressions that may pose offence or suggest an unpleasant idea to the receiver with a courteous

or pleasant expression, or to make it a less offensive expression for the speaker. Michael (2018) observes human beings have always recourse to euphemism imprecise and indirect statements in their quest to shy away from the harsh reality of life, and that in euphemistic usage of language, one expression is substituted by another. Euphemisms can also be used to describe someone or something in order to conceal the real identity of the subject of a discussion from would-be listeners or to prevent disclosing secret, holy, or sacred identities to the uninformed. Some presenters make an effort to say things that might not offend everyone. The selection of words that many consider to be mandatory. For a speech to be accepted by the listener, it is the speaker's duty to always be truly courteous. Euphemisms can be used to replace objectionable language. Words that were formerly meant to be euphemisms for forbidden phrases or words may no longer have referents. They could occasionally be used in a mocking or dysphoric manner. In Idoma language, euphemisms are used in the place of taboo expressions or words to protect the social norms of the communication during a speech.

The Field of Pragmatics

Some notable linguists have been able to provide their contributions of what they refer to as the meaning of pragmatics, despite the fact that a subfield of linguistics emerged in the late 1970s. Leech (1983) defines pragmatics as the study of linguistic meaning in connection with a given speech phenomenon (the context of an expression). The study of pragmatics focuses on language use and meaning aspects that depend on the addressee, the speaker, and other elements of the utterance context.

Speakers and writers frequently convey far more meaning than they intend for their readers or listeners to perceive. Generally speaking, they will presume that context can be used to infer certain meanings that are not explicitly stated in words. This presumption stems from their common experiences, morals, social mores, or worldview, which directs people to understand meanings that go beyond language or syntax. The ultimate objective is to accurately decipher the intended meaning of the speaker. A key concept in the study of pragmatics is the idea of the speaker's or writer's intended meaning.

Idoma People of Nigeria

There are over 2.5 million Idoma people living in the southern region of Benue state. They dominated nine of the state's municipal administrations. Otukpo, Ado, Ogbadibo, Apa, Obi, Oju, Ohimini, Okpokwu, and Orokam are a few of them. It is composed of a roughly defined geographical entity whose vast bounds reach from Igbo land in the south to Doma and Keena in the north. Additionally, it reaches Wukari in the east and Idah in the west (Michael, 2018).

It makes sense that several villages may trace their roots to a single progenitor, Iduh, who is revered as the "father" of all the other communities. Nine sons came from him: Ananawogeno, who bred the Igumale people; Olinaogwu, who bred the Ugboju people; Idum, who bred the Adoka people; Agabi, who bred the Otukpo people; Eje, who bred the Umogidi people in Adoka; Edeh, who bred

the Edumoga people; and Ode, who bred the Yala people in what is now known as Cross River. Agatu, Etilo, and Alago are among the Idoma people who live in Nassarawa in addition to Benue and the state of Cross River (Michael, 2018).

It's hard to say how long the Idomas have been in their current position. According to oral traditions, the Idoma people have resided in the Benue valley from ancient times. (Okpe & Ochefu, N.D). They settled in Apa cradle land in Kwaraafa kingdom before moving to their present location.

The headquarters of the Idoma people is Otukpo and they are headed by a king who is known as the Och'Idoma whose palace is in the heart of Otukpo. The Idoma people are a humble and hardworking people whose predominant occupation is farming. They grow crops like cassava, yam, corn, rice, palm fruits, soya beans, and so on. (Michael, 2018).

Idoma Language

Around one million people in Benue State, southeast-central Nigeria, speak Idoma as their second official language (Ethnologue, 2022). The Idoma language includes the varieties or dialects of Otukpo, Agatu, Orokam, Edumoga, Akpa Agila, Otukpa, Utonkon, Etilo, Igede, and Iyala. The Idoma people mostly hunt, cultivate, and fish. They are bordered to the south by Cross River State, north by Nasarawa State, west by Enugu and Kogi States, and east by Taraba State, (Ethnologue, 2022)

The Idoma people are a homogeneous ethnic group with dialectal distinctions, as seen by unique speech forms of people from Adoka, Otukpo, and Ugboju; Edumoga in contrast to Orokam, Agila, and Agatu, among others. Language evidence suggests that the Idoma people had resided in their current territory for at least five thousand years, and that they most likely travelled there from the north with the forefathers of the Yoruba, Bini, and Igbo people. All of these individuals are members of the Kwa language family, Michael (2018).

Theoretical Framework

This research work adopts politeness theory postulated by Brown and Levinson (1978) due to the fact that it is insightful in accounting for the forbidden aspects of language use. This can be related to certain words or expressions in the Idoma society, and how those expressions are used with substitutes (euphemisms). Politeness theory deals with how speakers sound polite to each other while communicating.

Brown and Levinson used the concept of 'face' in their theoretical work to show 'politeness' in a wide sense. This is to suggest that all interactants are interested in maintaining two forms of 'face' throughout interaction: 'positive face' and 'negative face'. Brown and Levinson describe a 'positive face' as a person's positive and consistent perception of themselves, as well as their need for acceptance. On the one hand, 'negative face' is "the basic claim to territories, personal preserves the right to non-distractions" (Brown and Levinson, 1978: 61) Some tenets of politeness theory include:

- **Positive face**

This is a person's kin desire to be appreciated and liked by other people. This can also be tagged a person's self-esteem. This face is expressed by the speaker.

- **Negative face**

On the other hand, this is a person's kin interest to defend their personal rights, be it their freedom of speech and action. This face is also expressed by the speaker.

One appeals to one of the two faces above when one shows politeness to another person.

- **Positive politeness**

This is a way of appealing to an individual's positive face, and it can also mean making the person feel good about themselves. This is an expression of politeness about someone else.

- **Negative politeness**

This is a way of appealing to an individual's negative face, and it can also mean making the other individual feel like they haven't been oppressed in the discourse or taken advantage of.

According to Brown and Levinson, when humans are disrespectful to individuals or restrict their personal liberties, they are doing face-threatening activities (directed at the persons they are speaking with). When they confess and apologise for their flaws, they do face-threatening activities (directed at themselves). They also argue that collaboration between speakers is required during social engagement. This is to keep both the speaker's face and the face of the person being chatted with intact.

Face is the "public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself". It refers to the social perception of self-image that every individual possesses, and expects others to acknowledge. According to face needs, sensible members of society would always strive to portray themselves in the best possible light. They seek to maintain their faces and portray themselves as worthy of respect, self-sufficient, pure, and devoid of dirty items that may jeopardise the integrity of their perceptions of themselves as courteous, thoughtful, and respected members of society (Brown & Levinson, 1987:61).

Therefore, this research sets to discuss how politeness theory theory can be applied in analysing the selected taboo words and expressions in Idoma language as it will aid in reflecting both the physical and linguistic image of the people. For example, demonstrating in public that one responds to nature's call or copulates as an innate need may contradict one's positive face demands. Douglas (1966) believes that by nature we are polite and euphemistic, and we regulate our choice of words to avoid taboo themes in pursuit of well-being for ourselves and others. Moreover, as a traditional society that took to Christianity not long ago, the Idoma society is immensely affected by Christian teachings and values that further regulates the usage of obscene words that obscene words based on belief that a faithful believer should not be vulgar nor does he or she use an

indecent choice of words. On this ground, this study shall make an effort to examine the phenomenon of taboo expressions in the Idoma society using the Brown and Levinson's politeness theory.

Methodology

Research design and Population Sampling

This study used a survey research design. The survey study design is gathering information on one or more groups of individuals, such as their opinions, attributes, experiences, attitudes, or by asking questions and tabulating the responses. The study's population included all speakers of the Idoma language, which was believed to be over 3.5 million individuals in Benue State at the time of the data gathering for this research (2021). Hence, the population that is sampled for this study is the native speakers of Idoma that are residing in Otukpo local government, being the largest of the Idoma province in Benue State. The Idoma native speakers above the age of 39 shall be sampled. People within this range are known to be more versed in the norms, customs, and traditional values of the targeted society.

Sampling technique and data collection

The purposive sampling technique is used for this study. This sampling technique is chosen to ensure that the data will be reliable and of good quality. Since this study investigates linguistic taboo, the instrument for collection is a questionnaire. Questionnaires are mostly used to collect information on the past, present, anticipated, and prevailing conditions and practices as they relate to the Idoma language. To authenticate the information received from the questionnaire, interviews are used where required.

Method of data analysis

This study adopted a qualitative approach to data analysis. A qualitative approach to research collects data in order to analyse a social circumstance, which could be in the form of spoken transcripts, written text, or other forms of documents that are analysed in an attempt to understand human behaviour and experiences in a social setting. A qualitative approach to data analysis is adopted for the identification, observation, description, discussion, and interpretation of the selected taboo words in the Idoma language. This approach is descriptive and discursive in nature. This approach is deemed appropriate since the study itself is a qualitative one.

Analysis and Discussion

In this part, the various forms of taboo expressions and their alternative usages will be analysed and discussed.

Usage of Taboo Expressions in Idoma Language

Taboo words do not only exist, but they are also used by the speakers of the Idoma language, though their use is restricted because society wants to uphold morality, encourage the polite use of words among the Idoma speakers, and avoid feelings of animosity. Taboo words are being used by

the Idoma speakers, mostly among their peers, in their discussions. Old women sometimes use taboo words amongst themselves due to the fact that they have gone beyond the age of childbearing. Hence, they tend to discuss using some taboo words because, to them, they have gone beyond the level of feeling ashamed of anything. Old men also use taboo words amongst themselves or, in some cases, among the company of old women while brooding over the locally made beer called *eje*.

Social related taboo expressions

These are taboo words that are used to disapprove or condemn people that partake in unbecoming acts that are considered as embarrassment to the Idoma people, as they are also deployed to ridicule individuals that engage in wild and uncontrollable behaviours so as to persuade them to change from that particular unruly behaviour.

S/N	Taboo Words	Glosses	Euphemisms	English Interpretation
1.	Ohe	Witch	Oche no gewu	One that flies
2.	Ofiye	Slave	OyiO'biba	An illegitimate child
3.	Uwi	Thief	O'yabolufiye	Being left handed
4.	Ukpo	Toilet	Oweche	The road that leads out
5.	Emi	Excretion	Ipachi	Bush
6.	Ataku	Lap	Ikpo	Leg
7.	O'ku	Death	O'hilenyo	Dropping ones breath

Table 1: Social related taboo expressions

In the table above, taboo expressions that relate to the social lives of Idoma people are presented. The expressions are capable of causing social embarrassment to whomever utters them in a speech event. For instance, it is forbidden for someone to mention 'O'ku' (death) during conversation or to explicitly declare that someone is 'dead'. Hence, the speaker must use the euphemism 'o'hilenvo' meaning 'dropping one's breath'. This is more appropriate in any context. This will show that the speaker is polite and save the speaker's face' from being humiliated. The "public self-image" of such a speaker will remain intact, according to the postulation of Brown and Levinson (1978:61).

Sex Related Taboo Expressions

Words belonging to this group are classified on moral basis or justification. This is because of their association with sex and to conform with the moral acceptable standard of the Idoma that they are forbidden. This is why they have alternatives that neutralise the unpleasantness, thereby creating euphemisms that will make them more acceptable and presentable.

S/N	Taboo Words	Glosses	Euphemism	English Interpretation
1.	Utu	Vagina	Agadak'onya	Between the legs of a woman
2.	Api	Penis	Iyobuk'onnyilo	The front part of a man

3.	Onyila	Menstruation	Oche no yaholohin	One who is not in a good shape
4.	Onyao'la	Sexual act	Ikponya	The laps of a woman
5.	Ame	Breast	Otukonya	The woman's chest
6.	Ajao'gbo	Adultery	O'likpotonu	Throwing one's leg around
7.	Akuna	Prostitution	Ochi o'kweche	Putting one's chair outside

Table 2: Sex Related Taboo Expressions

The table above shows some expressions that are related to sex and sexual discourse including the human genitals. In Idoma language and culture, the explicit using of such expressions and words is totally forbidden. For instance, an individual may say 'Iyobuk'onnyilo' meaning 'the front part of a man' instead of mentioning the explicit connotation of the expression 'api' meaning 'penis'. In this situation, the public self image of the speaker will be saved from being humiliated and the speaker will remain polite.

Culture related taboo expressions

These taboo expressions or words, in the Idoma language, are intended to accord respect to a particular class of people in the Idoma culture simply because it is a belief of the Idoma people that the higher one goes, the more respect that should be accorded to him.

S/N	Taboo Words	Glosses	Euphemisms	English Interpretation
1.	Oba	Husband	Ada'lo	Our father
2.	Onya	Wife	Ena'lo	Our mother
3.	Ad'oba	Father-in-law	Ada	Father
4.	En'oba	Mother-in-law	Ene	Mother

Table 3: Culture related taboo expressions

The table above presents some taboo expressions related to culture in terms of respect. In the Idoma language, some sets of people are not called by their real names or titles. Therefore, some alternatives (euphemisms) are used for them. People like husband, wife, father-in-law, and mother-in-law are not called explicitly by their appellations. Such is forbidden in Idoma language and culture. Anyone who is accustomed to the Idoma culture will take cognizance of these. For instance, a husband will call his wife 'ena'lo' meaning 'our mother' and not by her real name or her title. With this, the husband is being polite and respectful of the culture. This goes in accordance with Brown and Levinson's (1978) Face Savings Act.

Context of Using Taboo Words in Idoma Language

In the Idoma language, taboo words are used for a variety of purposes, one of which is insult. People tend to use taboo to express their anger so that the other person can feel how hurt they are because of their words. This is to show one's positive face and save one's self-public image. This will also give a negative face to the target of the taboo expressions, according to Brown and Levinson (1978). Some use taboo to express their frustration about a particular issue. Others use taboo to express insulting jokes, that is, jokes that are humorous and amusing. In some cases,

taboos are used by the Idoma speakers to express surprise. Taboos are also used to express hatred and hostility, especially towards children who are orphaned and are staying with relatives or children whose parents are poor and are taken to stay with relatives who are well-to-do.

Those that Taboo Words are used on

Taboos in Idoma are used on different kinds of people, one of which is young ladies who tend to go after men in the community. When such demoralising words are used against them, they tend to forsake their immoral ways because they do not want to be stigmatised in the community. Young ladies hate to be called *Akuna*, which means prostitute; hence, they tend to stay away from anything that will associate them with prostitution in order not to be stigmatised in the community. Young men or teenagers are also prevented from going into stealing because it is quite embarrassing to be referred to as *Uwi* in the community, which means thief. In the Idoma community, people hate to have anything that connects them to taboos, the reason being that they do not want society to treat them differently from others because they want to save their 'faces' and their names. This will bring about negative politeness for the victims.

Effects of Taboo Expressions on the Speaker

Although some people use taboo expression on people to make them decrease from associating themselves with taboo acts that attract taboo words or names on them. The breach in taboo expression or word usage in the Idoma community can lead to a number of consequences, one of which is that it leads to shame and embarrassment to whoever the taboo is used on and to the person who uses them. It brings disrespect to the person who breaches it because society frowns at its usage. The breach in the use of taboo also brings about hatred between the people who use them and those that it is used upon. To others, it brings about immorality and disassociation. For the above reasons, it is hard for Idoma speakers to use the language efficiently and adequately. Others are of the view that it is good that taboo is being placed on some Idoma words so as to induce morality among the language speakers. This means that despite the positive effects of the speakers using taboo words in the Idoma language, there are also negative implications that are detrimental to the language users.

Most people disagree with the view that Idoma taboo expressions should be taught in schools during Idoma language class, the reason being that it will help avoid immorality, misuse of the Idoma taboo expressions, and offending people. Others are of the view that Idoma taboo words should be taught in schools since they are a part of the language and will help learners understand what constitutes Idoma taboo expressions. Also, it will give Idoma language learners insight into the Idoma culture, which will aid in the maintenance of the language.

Socio-cultural Functions of Taboo Expressions

Taboo words have a variety of socio-cultural functions in the Idoma language. Firstly, it helps to define the Idoma culture and characterise the people who live in it. With the Idoma taboo

expressions, people who had no idea about the Idoma culture will have an insight into the culture of the Idoma people. It gives outsiders an insight into who the Idoma people are.

Taboo phrases or words function as a collection of social rules, helping to clarify the distinction between what is proper and unsuitable. Some of the forbidden terms in the Idoma language may seem foolish and unrealistic to others, but this is what distinguishes the Idoma culture. Taboos not only explain the distinction between the proper and inappropriate, but they also help individuals stay on the appropriate part to prevent shame or dishonour.

Idoma taboos help in the preservation of their cultural heritage and history. Idoma taboos not only constitute a part of the Idoma culture but also provide a good explanation of that heritage. Also, Idoma taboos help to maintain law, order, and harmony in the existence of society, which helps in the assurance of the continuation of life in its fullness in the Idoma community. Again, it enhances the quality of life and preserves the social code of behaviour in the Idoma community.

Conclusion

Taboo expressions remain cultural emblems of the Idoma language with their distinctive usages. From the data presented and analysed above, the meaning of linguistic taboo among the Idoma people of Benue State differs from one language speaker to another. The situation of the use of taboo words in the Idoma language varies from one concept to another. The findings of the study show that there are various forms of taboo expressions, which include social sex and culture-related taboo expressions. The study also identifies the factors that are militating against the use of Idoma taboo words such as shame, immorality, indecency, and the fear of being sanctioned by society, which often occur as disassociation. Despite these factors and their restrictions on usage, elderly people who have passed through the age of being shameful use taboo among themselves, especially during jokes, and to instill morals in young ones. To avoid the extinction of some vital expressions in language, this study recommends that taboo expressions in the Idoma language be used in private discussions among couples, friends, and relatives. Also, writers of Idoma texts should endeavour to document all aspects of the Idoma taboo expressions. This research has contributed to the extant literature on the Idoma language on the aspect of politeness through the usage of taboo expressions. Further studies can be carried out on the cultural and ideological implications of taboo usage and how taboo expressions should be taught to the young so as to know how to use or avoid them.

Author Contributions

Introduction, Analysis and Discussion, Ajayi, O.B	(40%)
Literature Review and Methodology, Analysis and Discussion, Kilani S.O.	(40%)
Data Gathering and Translation, Michael, M.E	(20%)

References

- Allan, K., & Burrige, K. (2006). *Forbidden Words. Taboo and the Censoring of Language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511617881>
- Britannica, T. Information Architects of Encyclopaedia (2024, February 15). Taboo. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/facts/taboo-sociology>
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: Some Universals in Language Usage*. Cambridge University Press.
- Douglas, M. (1966). *Purity and Danger*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203361832>
- Ethnologue: Languages of the World (2022). Dallas, Texas: SIL International.
- Fairman, C-M. (2009). *Fuck – Word taboo and protecting our first amendment liberties*. Illinois: Sphinx Publishing an imprint of Sourcebooks Inc.
- Leech, G. N. (1983). *Principles of Pragmatics*. London: Longman.
- Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mercury, R.-E. (1995). Swearing: A “Bad” Part of Language; A Good Part of Language Learning. *TESL Canada Journal*, 13(1), 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.18806/tesl.v13i1.659>
- Michael, M.E. (2018). *A sociolinguistic analysis of selected taboo words in Idoma language*. Undergraduate project, Federal University Wukari.
- Okpe, O.O. & Ochefu, Y. A (N.D.). *The Idoma Ethnic Group: A Historical and Cultural Setting*. 1-51. Retrieved on March 10, 2024 from https://www.academia.edu/9195474/The_Idoma_of_Central_Nigeria
- Trudgill P. (2000). *Sociolinguistics: an introduction to language and society* (4th ed.). Penguin.